

Final report ELIXIRxNextGenIT Access

1st National Open Access Call

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1. Introduction

The primary mission of Research Infrastructures (RIs) is to support researchers within a specific scientific domain. Among the various ways in which an RI can provide this support are open access calls. TNA/NOA programmes are initiatives aimed at supporting scientists by providing them with free access to the facilities, equipment, expertise, services, and resources of Research Infrastructures (RIs) that they would not normally be able to access. Access to RI services can take three different forms:

- Physical access: when research staff physically travel to the RI and use its instruments and resources on site.
- Virtual access: when the services provided can be used at a distance by the researcher. A typical example is access to computing resources.
- Remote access: when the researcher makes use of RI services without accessing the infrastructure directly. A typical example is the shipment of samples for the performance of agreed analyses (send-in-sample).

The 1st Call of ELIXIRxNextGenIT for National Open Access was launched to provide the life-science research community with free remote access to advanced ELIXIR-IT Omics Platform services in the fields of Genomics and Metabolomics.

The call was implemented within the framework of the **ELIXIRxNextGenIT project** and aimed to support researchers by enabling access to facilities, expertise, technologies, and data/results repository services that may not otherwise be available within their own institutions.

The National Open Access model adopted for this call was based on a remote “send-in-sample” modality. Users were therefore not required to physically access the facilities; instead, samples were sent to the relevant access provider, where the analyses were carried out by qualified technical and scientific staff.

The services were delivered through the following ELIXIR-IT access providers:

- ELIXIR-IT Facility at O.U. CNR-IBIOM, CNR, Istituto di Biomembrane, Bioenergetica e Biotecnologie Molecolari;
- ELIXIR-IT Facility at O.U. University of Bari, Università di Bari Aldo Moro – Dipartimento di Bioscienze, Biotecnologie e Ambiente;
- ELIXIR-IT / OASI Metabolomics Facility at O.U. CNR-IBSBC, CNR, Istituto di Bioimmagini e Sistemi Biologici Complessi.

2. Preparation of the Call

Before the publication of the call, the documentation and operational procedures required for its proper implementation were prepared. This included the definition of participation rules, eligibility requirements, available services, technical specifications, legal conditions, and user obligations.

Four working groups were established to support the implementation of the call:

- the user support group acted as the main interface between applicants and the research infrastructure, supporting potential users in understanding the call requirements, verifying eligibility criteria, and carrying out formal checks on submitted documents.
- the technical support group, composed of facility managers and technical staff, addressed user questions related to service feasibility, sample requirements, technical specifications, and analysis procedures.
- the legal advisory group was provided by the ELIXIR-IT ELSI officer, who supported the clarification of ethical and legal aspects and liaised with the legal offices of applicant organisations for the finalisation of the User Access Agreements.
- the scientific committee, composed by the facility managers, the head of node of ELIXIR-IT and the scientific coordinator of ELIXIRxNextGenIT. It was in charge of the evaluation of applications.

The following documents were prepared and made available to applicants:

- Guidelines;
- Service Catalogue;
- Application Form;
- Project Proposal template;
- User Access Agreement;
- Acceptable User Policy, Terms of Use, and Privacy Policy of Service for the Omics platform.

3. Publication and Dissemination

The call was officially announced by CNR on 10 March 2025 and published on the ELIXIR-IT website. It was also disseminated through the main communication channels of the Italian Node ([Sito web CNR-NOA CS](#); [\[ELIXIR Italy website; ELIXIR Europe – Italy Node\]](#)).

The call remained open until 15 April 2025. During this period, applicants were invited to submit their proposals by email, following the instructions provided in the guidelines and related documentation.

The call announcement described the scope of the initiative, the services offered, the access modality, the list of access providers, the application procedure, the available documentation, and the selection process.

4. Support to Applicants During the Call

During the opening period of the call, the support group received requests from 52 users. Most contacts came from academic institutions (69%), with additional requests from private research institutes (11%), IRCCS (11%), and public research institutes (9%).

Out of the 52 users who contacted the support group, 41 submitted a formal application for access to the services.

The requests received during the call mainly concerned:

- technical aspects of the services;
- clarification on access procedures;
- general information on the call and its requirements.

This interaction with potential applicants was an important part of the call management process, as it helped ensure that users could identify the most appropriate service, understand the technical requirements, and prepare complete applications.

5. Evaluation Process

The applications submitted were evaluated by the Scientific Committee,

The evaluation considered the consistency between the proposed scientific project and the requested service, both in terms of the type of analysis requested and the number of analyses proposed.

Applications were also assessed in relation to the available budget and the overall feasibility of the requested services.

In order to accommodate the highest possible number of scientifically and technically suitable projects, the Scientific Committee proposed a rescheduling of the number of samples for some applications.

Following this process, **39 projects** were admitted to access and the corresponding project leads signed the User Access Agreements.

6. Service Delivery and Release of Results

The results of the services were delivered to the respective project leads in April 2026.

Data transfer was carried out through secure file-transfer tools based on the [OpenSSH](#)/SSH protocol. For human-origin data, an additional encryption layer was

implemented using crypt4gh, in line with the [GA4GH File Encryption Standard](#) to support the secure management of confidential genomic and health-related files [[OpenSSH](#); [GA4GH File Encryption Standard](#)].

This approach ensured that data were transferred through secure and appropriate procedures, taking into account the nature of the data and the legal and ethical requirements associated with their handling.

7. Unit Cost methodology and financial reporting

The implementation of the National Open Access programme was supported by the adoption of the Unit Cost methodology, used both as an operational planning tool and as a basis for the financial reporting of the services delivered through the ELIXIR-IT OMICS Platform.

In the context of EU research funding, Trans-national Access (TNA) Unit Costs refer to the simplified cost methodology provided by the European Commission to support researchers' access to European Research Infrastructures. Although the ELIXIRxNextGenIT call was implemented as a National Open Access initiative, the calculation of the service costs was based on the European Commission model for TNA access costs, adapted to the national access framework of the project.

According to the Horizon Europe framework, the calculation of Unit Costs follows a structured approach. Financial administrators calculate the access costs using the official European Commission TNA Calculation Template ensuring a harmonised, transparent, and reproducible approach to the definition of the access costs.

In accordance with the European Commission model, ineligible costs and costs already declared under other budget categories were excluded from the calculation in order to avoid double funding. The calculation therefore supported both the transparent management of access to the infrastructure and the correct financial reporting of the services provided free of charge to users under the NOA call.

The Unit Cost model adopted for the ELIXIR-IT OMICS Platform was formally approved by the Italian Ministry of University and Research (MUR), ensuring alignment with national and European funding rules and supporting the transparent, comparable, and sustainable management of access to the infrastructure.

8. User Satisfaction Survey

After data transfer and receipt of the final service report, users were invited to complete a service satisfaction questionnaire.

At the close of the survey, 33 out of 39 users had completed the questionnaire, corresponding to a response rate of 84.61%.

The questionnaire covered the following areas:

- general information on the applicant;
- access experience;
- usefulness of the resources;
- overall satisfaction;
- feedback and suggestions.

Overall, the results show a positive assessment of the National Open Access experience. Users appreciated the availability of advanced technologies, the quality of the generated data, the professionalism of the access providers, and the opportunity to perform analyses that would otherwise have been outside the technical or financial capacity of their laboratories.

The comments received also highlight the importance of technical support and direct interaction with the access providers, which were perceived as valuable elements of the programme.

8.1. Main Feedback from Users

The most appreciated aspects of the NOA experience included:

- access to high-quality sequencing and metabolomics services;
- the opportunity to use advanced technologies free of charge;
- the professionalism and technical expertise of service providers;
- clear and useful guidance on sample preparation;
- positive communication with the access providers;
- the possibility to generate data relevant to ongoing research projects, including PhD projects.

At the same time, users identified some aspects that could be improved in future calls. The most recurrent suggestions concerned:

- reducing the time required for data processing and data release;
- simplifying or improving data transfer procedures;
- providing clearer timelines for sample processing and result delivery;
- improving communication on sample quality requirements during the project planning phase;
- considering the inclusion of bioinformatics data analysis services;
- evaluating mechanisms to make the call more regular and continuous over time.

These suggestions provide useful input for improving the organisation of future NOA calls and for strengthening the user experience across all phases of access.

9. Final Remarks

The **1st Call of ELIXIRxNextGenIT for National Open Access** can be considered successful in terms of participation, service delivery, and user satisfaction.

The call generated significant interest from the Italian research community, as shown by the number of users who contacted the support group and the number of applications submitted. The high conversion rate from initial contact to formal application suggests that the documentation, communication, and support provided during the call were effective.

The admission of **39 projects** demonstrates the capacity of ELIXIR-IT to coordinate access to advanced omics services through a structured national access procedure. The delivery of results in April 2026 completed the access process and enabled users to benefit from high-quality data and technical expertise.

Survey results confirm a generally positive experience among users. The majority of respondents expressed satisfaction with the programme, and several comments highlighted the scientific value of the services, the quality of the data received, and the professionalism of the access providers.

The main areas for improvement concern the timing of data delivery, the simplification of data transfer procedures, and the possibility of providing clearer timelines and additional downstream support, including bioinformatics analysis.

Overall, the first NOA call represents a relevant step in strengthening access to ELIXIR-IT services at national level and provides a valuable model for future calls. The lessons learned from this first implementation should be used to further consolidate the process, improve communication with users, and support a more stable and regular access mechanism over time.

10. Annexes

The following annexes should be included as supporting documentation:

Annex 1 – Call Guidelines;

Annex 2 – Service Catalogue;

Annex 3 – Application Form;

Annex 4 – Project Proposal Template;

Annex 5 – User Access Agreement;

Annex 6 – AUP, Terms of Use, and Privacy Policy of Service;

Annex 7 - UNIT COST

Annex 8 – Report on User Satisfaction Survey. Results, Open Feedbacks and suggestions;